

CHEMICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CO-CURED HYBRID COMPOSITE/ALUMINIUM STRUCTURES

S. Mercier¹, R. Agogue², A. Mavel³ and P. Nunez⁴

¹Department of Metallic Materials and Structures, Onera, the French Aerospace Lab
29 avenue de la division Leclerc, 92322 Châtillon, France
Email: sebastien.mercier@onera.fr, web page: <http://www.onera.fr>

²Department of Composite Materials and Structures, Onera, the French Aerospace Lab
29 avenue de la division Leclerc, 92322 Châtillon, France
Email: romain.agogue@onera.fr, web page: <http://www.onera.fr>

³Department of Composite Materials and Structures, Onera, the French Aerospace Lab
29 avenue de la division Leclerc, 92322 Châtillon, France
Email: anne.mavel@onera.fr, web page: <http://www.onera.fr>

⁴Department of Composite Materials and Structures, Onera, the French Aerospace Lab
29 avenue de la division Leclerc, 92322 Châtillon, France
Email: philippe.nunez@onera.fr, web page: <http://www.onera.fr>

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ABSTRACT

The use of hybrid materials where the right material is used at the right place for its best properties is of great interest for structures optimisation, particularly when mass reduction is required. In such hybrid structures, where metal and composite are closely in contact, the strength of the interface between the metal and the composite is fundamental to obtain good mechanical performances of the system.

This paper is related to the mechanical and chemical properties of Aluminium/CFRP hybrid materials. It concerns the influence of the aluminium surface treatment on the interface properties obtained after a one step co-curing manufacturing process. Two different aerospace aluminium alloys (Al-2024 and Al-2198) were first treated either by tartaric-sulphuric anodizing (TSA), chromic acid anodizing (CAA) or silane pre-treatments. In order to characterize the galvanic corrosion behaviour of the Al/CFRP hybrid system, Evans diagram were plotted in a 3% NaCl solution with treated aluminium alloys as anodic part, and with composite material or isolated carbon fibres as cathodic part. The galvanic coupling and the corrosion current were determined. Al/CFRP single-lap joint tensile test samples were manufactured by an innovative one step co-curing process and tested in order to characterize the strength of the interface.

The results of this study shows that the pre-treatment of the aluminium have an influence on corrosion properties of the interface, but almost no influence on mechanical properties. The results are discussed and a hierarchical organisation of the treatments was established in order to facilitate the choice of the best configuration. This study has also permitted to highlight different solutions to optimize the durability of such an assembly.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composite/metal structures already exist for aerospace applications. These hybrid structures are mainly made of composite for their good performance to weight ratio. Metal inserts are generally used so as to fill the lack of composite performances, such as conductivity or joining.

The classical industrial process used for hybrid structure is to manufacture the composite and metal components separately, prepared them before performing the assembly step to get the final hybrid structure. This process is time consuming and some operations, such as drilling of the composite material, could drastically reduce its performances. To overcome this situation, this study focuses on hybrid structures made by a one step co-curing process.

In such hybrid structures, where metal and composite are closely in contact, the strength of the interface between metal and composite is fundamental to obtain a good junction. It is well known that metal pre-treatments like chromate conversion or anodizing is beneficial to the adherence of polymers on aluminium [1, 2, 3]. These processes are for example commonly used in painted aluminium structures or aluminium adhesive bonding in aerospace industry.

It is therefore of great interest to study the influence of such aluminium treatments in increasing interface properties in hybrid aluminium/composite structures and to assess the durability of these properties after exposure to humid or corrosive environment.

The dichromate etching and chromic acid anodizing are well known to improve adhesion between aluminium and polymers in adhesive joining or painting systems, but, due to its CrVI compounds contained, these treatments are concerned by the REACh regulation and have to be substituted by CrVI-free processes.

In this study, The Chromic Acid Anodizing (CAA) has been chosen as a reference and compared to CrVI-free Tartaric Sulphuric Anodizing (TSA) and γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane silanization (γ -GPS) treatments. The three treatments have been applied to Al-2024 and Al-2198 aluminium alloys and characterised after co-curing in terms of galvanic corrosion and mechanical properties of the interface.. The galvanic corrosion has been determined on untreated and treated Al-2024/CFRP or Al-2198/CFRP coupling by the Evans diagram method. The mechanical strength of the interface between Al-2024 or Al-2198 and CFRP has been determined with co-cured Al/CFRP single lap joints (SLJ) mechanical tests in order to compare the bonding strength obtained with the different treatments of the aluminium alloy.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The materials selected for this study were a Al-2024 aluminium alloy (composition in wt.%: 4.4% Cu, 1.50% Mg, 0.6% Mn, Al bal.), a Al-2198 aluminium alloy (Composition in wt.%: 3.2% Cu, 0.95% Li, 0.53% Mg, 0.3% Ag, 0.11% Zr) and a CFRP quasi-isotropic UD laminate (T700GC/M21, Hexcel Composites) made from prepreg.

For galvanic corrosion measurements, 10 x 10 x 4 mm coupons were cut in two 4 mm thick Al-2024 and Al-2198 sheets. two 10 x 10 x 4 mm coupons were cut in a CFRP in order to expose the face in contact of the aluminium alloy in the co-cured material as shown on Figure 1.

Face in contact with the aluminium alloy

Figure 1: Description of the CFRP used in the study and identification of the face tested in galvanic corrosion measurements.

For single lap joint tensile tests, 125 x 156 x 8 mm hybrid plates, made of two overlapped foils of Al-2024//Epoxy/Carbon fibres and Al-2198//epoxy/carbon fibres were prepared by a co-curing process (Figure 2). The first foil was made of composite whereas the second one was made of aluminium. Each layer had the same size of 125 x 90 x 4 mm. The overlapping distance was set to 24 mm. The thickness of the test specimens was designed to avoid any plasticity effect during the mechanical tests.

The following step were followed for the co-cured process: (i) aluminium sheet was put into the mould, after being prepared; (ii) The plies were deposited according to the stacking sequence; (iii) A

two hours dwell at 180°C was performed to consolidate the composite, following the manufacturer's recommendations. In addition, a pressure of 6 bars was applied to composite during curing. The composite / aluminium interface was generated before gelation of the polymer when the resin flows from prepreg to the interface; (iv) Finally, four 24 x 156 x 8 mm SJL specimens were machined in each co-cured plates.

Figure 2: Al/composite specimen preparation for SLJ tensile tests.

Before manufacturing of hybrid materials, the aluminium samples were prepared as follows:

The surface of the alloy samples was cleaned with ethanol and deionised water. Alkaline cleaning for the samples was carried out in a 10% NaOH solution for 15 min at 60 °C. After water cleaning, the samples were rinsed in deionised water and etched in a 30% nitric acid solution for 10 min at room temperature. The samples were then cleaned with deionised water and dried for 30 min at 80°C. Chromic Acid Anodizing (CAA), Tartaric Sulphuric Anodizing (TSA) or γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane silanization (γ -GPS) were used as shown in Table 1.

Process	Composition		Conditions
1- Chromic Acid Anodizing	CrO ₃	50 g/L	Anodizing at 40°C, 40V during 20 min, then 50V during 10 min
2- Tartaric Sulfuric Anodizing	C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	80 g/L	Anodizing at 35°C, 15V during 30 min
	H ₂ SO ₄	45 g/L	
3- γ -GPS silanization	γ -GPS	1% vol.	dipping for 10 min, air drying, condensation during 60 min at 80°C

Table 1: Surface preparation of the aluminium samples before corrosion tests or co-curing of hybrid material specimens.

The pre-treated samples were tested in corrosion tests or co-cured with the CFRP before one hour after the pre-treatment.

The galvanic corrosion was evaluated by the Evans method using polarisation curves of aluminium alloys and CFRP specimens. The polarisation curves were measured using a model 273A potentiostat in a neutral 3.5% NaCl solution at room temperature (20 °C). The potential scanning rate was 1 mV. s⁻¹. A saturated Ag/AgCl electrode was used as the reference electrode, and the counter electrode was platinum. The specimens were coated with epoxy resin to isolate the sample and the electric connection, leaving one face exposed to the solution during the electrochemical testing. The surface of each specimen was measured before testing and the current densities presented in this paper were normalized to this measured area.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Manufacturing of co-cured composite/aluminium mechanical test samples

The co-cured process was tested with two different aluminium alloys and three surface treatments. The six configurations selected are presented on Table 2.

Alloy	surface pre-treatment	composite layup
Al-2024	Chromic acid anodizing	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic
Al-2024	Tartric sulfuric anodizing	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic
Al-2024	γ -GPS silanization	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic
Al-2198	Chromic acid anodizing	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic
Al-2198	Tartric sulfuric anodizing	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic
Al-2198	γ -GPS silanization	T700M21, 16 plies, quasi-isotropic

Table 2: test matrix for the mechanical assessment of the interface properties.

Two kinds of defects were analysed on produced samples: porosity and shape distortion due to residual stress after the cooling down step of the curing process.

The assessment of the porosity rate was performed using cross-sectional observations of the samples and a low rate of porosity was found.

Concerning shape distortions, some authors have observed geometrical distortions due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite and the metal layer on hybrid structures [4, 5]. Consequently, the curvature of samples presented on Table 2 was measured and found to be very small in comparison to the sample typical length. Consequently, the effect of residual stress and residual strain is neglected in this paper.

3.2 Galvanic corrosion measurements

The galvanic current and potential determination was carried out using the Evans method. This method consists in measuring the polarisation curve of the two constitutive materials in the aggressive media and in constructing the galvanic coupling in representing on the same graph, the anodic part of the aluminium polarisation curve and the absolute value of the cathodic part of the composite curve. The Figure 3 shows an example of the obtained Evans diagrams of the unprotected Al-2024 coupled with the CFRP or an isolated non-impregnated carbon fibre yarns. For each coupling configuration the same diagram was established and the coupling potentials and coupling current densities was determined. The results are summarised in the Table 3.

It can be seen that whatever the treatment, a decreasing of the galvanic corrosion current can be observed for both tested alloys. The efficiency of the treatment in galvanic coupling situation is similar to what has been previously observed on polarisation curves. The CAA treatment is by far the best treatment. The galvanic current is divided by about 2 to 5 for Al-2024, and divided by 2 to 7 for Al-2198. The efficiency of TSA or silanization is different depending of the considered alloy. For Al-2024 alloy, the γ -GPS silanization is better than TSA. The galvanic current is divided by a factor 2 to 3 for γ -GPS whereas it is only divided by a factor 1.5 to 2 for TSA. For Al-2198 alloy, the TSA is better than γ -GPS. The galvanic current is divided by a factor 2 to 2.7 for TSA, whereas there is almost no effect of γ -GPS treatment on galvanic current on Al-2198.

A ranking of the aluminium alloys treatments regarding the anti-corrosive effect in galvanic corrosion situation can therefore be established from these measurements. For the Al-2024 alloy, the ranking is the following: CAA is better than γ -GPS which is better than TSA. For the Al-2198 alloy, the ranking is the following: CAA is better than TSA which is better than γ -GPS.

Figure 3: Example of Evans diagrams obtained for untreated 2024 alloy coupled with 1/ the CFRP specimen and 2/ the isolated carbon fibres yarns.

The Evans diagrams can also compare the effect of carbon fibres themselves on the galvanic coupling between the aluminium alloy and the CFRP. It can be seen from Table 3 that the galvanic corrosion current is about 8 to 25 times higher in the case of direct coupling with carbon fibres yarn than in the case of coupling with the CFRP. This result shows the fundamental effect of the conductive carbon fibres in the galvanic corrosion behavior of metal/CFRP structures.

The presence of the epoxy resin between the carbon fibres in the CFRP increases the electrical resistivity of the interface, and thus reduces the galvanic current density compared to the case of direct coupling of carbon fibres and aluminium alloys. However, it has to be noticed that the galvanic current density measured in the CFRP coupling is relative to an average current density measured on the total surface of the specimen. Actually, this average low value is hidden by the fact that the measured low current density is mainly due to the low contact areas between the alloy and the carbon fibres in that configuration. The local current density should probably be as high as the current density obtained in the case of direct coupling between aluminium alloy and carbon fibres, suggesting that if the main corrosion speed is low, the local one can be very high and damage the interface anyway.

Alloy	coupling with CFRP		coupling with Carbon fibres	
	E corr (V/NHE)	i corr (A/cm ²)	E corr (V/NHE)	i corr (A/cm ²)
2024	-0.529	3.09E-06	-0.519	1.13E-04
2024 + CAA	-0.444	1.61E-06	-0.362	1.98E-05
2024 + TSA	-0.476	2.11E-06	-0.442	5.32E-05
2024 + γ -GPS	-0.423	1.30E-06	-0.409	3.61E-05
2198	-0.523	2.98E-06	-0.501	9.63E-05
2198 + CAA	-0.440	1.55E-06	-0.334	1.35E-05
2198 + TSA	-0.433	1.44E-06	-0.409	3.61E-05
2198 + γ -GPS	-0.507	2.68E-06	-0.495	9.08E-05

Table 3: Potential and coupling current density for coupling between untreated and treated 2024 and 2198 alloys and three CFRP configurations (hypothesis: unitary and equal area of electrodes).

3.3 Mechanical characterization of the interface

The interface strength of manufactured samples (Table 2) was assessed using the single lap joint test. Tests were carried out at a constant strain velocity of 1mm/s until the ultimate load was reached. So as to characterize the experimental dispersion, three samples for each configuration were tested coming from the same plate.

The lap-shear ultimate loads of the samples are presented on Figure 4. On this figure, error bars represent the standard deviation of the three measurements.

Figure 4: Effect of aluminium pre-treatments on the ultimate loads of 11-2024 and Al-2198 using single lap joint testing

CAA is known to provide high interface strength [3] and is considered as a reference in this study. Figure 4 shows that TSA and γ -GPS provide a similar interface strength as CAA.

It was also observed that coupons initially located in the middle of the plate shows a higher and more repeatable ultimate strength than the samples located nearby the plate-edges. This finding could explain the rather large experimental dispersion observed for TSA-2024 and CAA-2198 results. This edge effect is probably due to a non-uniform surface pre-treatment of the aluminium alloys before curing.

4 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

A process of co-curing of composite/aluminium structures was presented. This process was used with two different aluminium alloys: one Al-2024 alloy and one Al-2198 alloy. Several surface treatments of the aluminium alloy were used to improve the interface properties between the polymer matrix of the composite and the aluminium substrate. These surface treatments were characterized in terms of galvanic corrosion resistance and in terms of mechanical strength. The galvanic corrosion behaviour was measured by the Evans diagram method, and the interface properties were assessed using the SLJ test.

According to the Evans diagrams, it appears that the Chromic Acid Anodizing is the best treatment for both alloys, but that Tartaric Sulphuric Anodizing or Silanization could represent a good alternative treatment in the condition of choosing the right treatment for the right alloy. The TSA treatment should be chosen for the Al-2198 alloy whereas the γ -GPS silanization treatment should be chosen for the Al-2024 alloy.

According to the results of the SLJ tests, the three tested pre-treatment of the aluminium alloys gave a similar interface strength in the hybrid co-cured structure.

Thus TSA and γ -GPS appear to be suitable candidates for the substitution of CAA treatments in terms of mechanical properties. However, the anti-corrosion properties of CAA still better than TSA and γ -GPS, suggesting that the galvanic corrosion could damage the interface during the life time of the structure, in particular for aerospace applications. It could then be important to assess the interface properties after long exposure to corrosive environment and to work on alternative solutions including electrical isolation between the CFRP and the alloy.

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